

ON THE NATURE OF THE SYSTEMIC CRISIS OF HUMANITY

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From time to time, humanity drives itself into deep states of crisis and catastrophe. Yet, every subsequent time, it disregards the lessons of history, committing new errors. The modern world has arrived at a global systemic crisis without even grasping its core essence, although the answers regarding the nature of these problems and the paths to resolve them lie directly on the surface.

Let us begin with what must be understood and transformed first.

THE IMBALANCE WITHIN THE SYSTEM OF RIGHTS AND RESPONSIBILITIES

All crises – both subjective (dependent on human actions and choices) and objective (completely independent of human understanding) – arise due to an imbalance within a given system. The disruption of equilibrium is the primary cause of all crises and catastrophes in the universe without exception. This can be easily understood through the example of rights and responsibilities. Their fundamental imbalance generates the conditions for crises and subsequent societal and human catastrophes, regardless of the level of relations within society or between humanity and nature.

Everywhere, the declaration of human rights is defended, granting people freedoms and privileges. Yet, nowhere is there a declaration of human responsibilities, which are absolutely necessary to exercise those rights responsibly. The desire to realize the rights of some leads to an inadequate imposition of responsibilities onto others, to whom the exact same rights were promised. Frequently, those responsible for the realization of these rights are not defined at all, leading to uncertainty, injustice, and conflict within society. As this imbalance accumulates, a systemic social crisis emerges, capable of escalating into revolution and catastrophe.

For every right, there must be an adequate, corresponding responsibility, just as for every responsibility, the necessary right must be granted. Although individual rights and responsibilities are rarely equivalent, they must be balanced at a higher systemic level: at the level of the individual, the family, society, and in the relationship between humans and nature. As soon as this principle is violated, the causes for conflicts, personal crises, economic breakdowns, social turmoils, and anthropogenic or natural disasters are born.

However, in the era of capitalism we are currently experiencing, everything is built upon the systemic violation of this principle. The misappropriation of resources and surplus value, alongside the formation of unequal opportunities, are the primary causes systematically generating crises under capitalism. Legislation and justice stand guard over special interests rather than the balance of rights and responsibilities.

THE CRISIS OF WORLDVIEW

We live in a world governed by rigid templates, inadequate concepts, and established dogmas; we accept highly questionable theories, hypotheses, and even illusions as absolute axioms. Therefore, if we wish to rethink anything and find answers to dead-end questions, we must break the templates of our own thinking and dismantle established dogmas.

All around us and within each of us lies a worldview kitsch, where three mutually exclusive paradigms simultaneously coexist: the religious (archaic, yet resurrected due to the unconscious

protest of the masses against a chaotic present and uncertain future), Modernism, and Postmodernism. All of them share a fundamental flaw: they are rooted in subjectivism without a proper understanding of the laws of the objective world, leaving humanity a hostage to itself in a state where both meaning and form are lost.

The cornerstone of the **religious worldview** is God, whose existence must be accepted on faith rather than rational understanding. Such a worldview is traditionally deemed irrational, yet it frequently provides a necessary understanding of acceptable behavioral boundaries much better than purely rational methods. However, because religion defined the "whole" through the prism of God, science, in moving away from archaic representations of the Lord, rejected the irrational altogether.

The irrational is not something divine, unreal, or non-rational, as commonly believed. It is that which must be comprehended as a whole, as a complete image or integrated concept. All the macro-blocks of information that each of us creates, stores, and operates with are direct manifestations of an irrational method of thinking and world-understanding. The more information we receive, the more we are forced to think in large blocks; and this does not mean it is incorrect, even if it falls outside the constraints of formal logic.

The **worldview of Modernism** was built upon the fundamental question of philosophy regarding the primacy of matter versus consciousness. In opposition to religious, irrational idealism, Modernism placed the world in total dependence upon rational logic and materialism. Irrational methods were discarded, and the world began to be viewed solely in pieces, without any comprehension of the whole.

However, baryonic matter in the Universe constitutes only about 4%; the rest consists of dark matter (23%) and dark energy (73%), the true nature of which remains completely unknown. Thus, Modernism imposed upon us a "four-percent worldview": we are convinced that everything can be understood exclusively through the logic of this minor fraction.

Consequently, even the laws of conservation should be perceived merely as the dogmas of the Modernist era. They are indeed universal, but strictly for the material world. We stubbornly project them onto the entirety of creation, refusing to tolerate alternative thoughts, thereby severely limiting science and world-understanding.

The Modernist worldview convinced man that he is the king of nature, and man successfully overcame his dependence on it. He did not stop there; he attempted to place nature in total dependence upon himself, transforming it from a habitat into a mere resource for "limitless" economic activity. Nature has begun to retaliate for this severe violation of the balance of rights and responsibilities, resulting in an escalating number of natural cataclysms.

Capitalism, emerging directly from Modernism, views everything as a resource – including human beings and society. Society is forced to function under the laws of a factory, where the primary public institutions became the school and the army. The school refines labor resources to the level required by the factory, while the army ensures societal cohesion in opposition to competing societies. The state substituted the organic functions of society, inevitably establishing a fierce competition of states, nations, economies, armies, and various academic schools.

Capitalism views everything through the narrow lens of competition. Even most modern games and mass sports are built upon competition or "cooperation" within a competitive struggle, while genuine cooperation has been discarded into the zone of "cultural heritage", ceasing to be a mass phenomenon.

Man becomes a mere cog in the system, generating a sharp conflict of the individual – who strives for freedom and self-realization – with a state-personified society that imposes strict frameworks and constraints upon everyone.

Following a brief surge in abstract thinking on the ruins of religion, which increasingly contradicted the pragmatic goals of capitalism, man began to be valued solely for his practical skills. The replacement of the thinking human (*Homo sapiens*) with the merely "educated human" began – an individual capable of choosing standard answers to standard questions from a predetermined list. The standardized human became preferable to the thinking human, and

individuals are turning into "standardized economic specimens", perceiving domestic comfort, technologies, and information as the ultimate good, utterly incapable of stepping outside the boundaries of their mounting ignorance about the universe and their deep fear of losing economic status.

This conflict between the individual and society birthed **Postmodernism**. At its core lies the doctrine of the complete absence of unified norms and rules, placing the subject – with all his vices, desires, and imperfect nature – at the absolute center of the world. Postmodernism became the worldview of subjectivism and chaos, presented as a path toward human freedom (or, rather, absolute permissiveness). Intersecting with capitalism, Postmodernist ideas formed even grander contradictions within man and society.

Every individual, by his very nature, is a creator of personal chaos, currently celebrated as the "manifestation of personal freedom". This chaos reproduces in an accelerating progression. Only society is capable of eliminating it by establishing rules and orders. Yet, Postmodern society itself is rapidly disintegrating under the assault of individual interests and general uncertainty, giving way to a "mere collection of disconnected individuals".

Capitalism has become a universal kitsch worldview, absorbing and mixing Modernism, Postmodernism, and religious world-understanding into a single entity, with the economy established as its absolute core. Now, all crises are misperceived as purely "economic", whereas we are facing a profound crisis of worldview.

THE CRISIS OF KNOWLEDGE AND SCIENCE

Relatively holistic, macro-block knowledge of the world can only be provided by philosophy, provided it maintains an initial emphasis on general concepts, metaphysics, and cosmology. However, philosophy has entirely departed into the study of subjective representations of man and society, practicing the manipulation thereof.

Philosophy possesses a strict scale according to which the entire diversity of (1) lifestyles depends on (2) available technologies. Technologies and their application depend on (3) methods of organization or the system of social relations. These relations depend on (4) the societal worldview, which is fundamentally rooted in (5) its ontological first principles.

Modern world-understanding is reduced solely to lifestyles, technologies, and occasionally to discussions about methods of organization. However, these representations can completely invert in the event of transformations at more fundamental levels – especially regarding changes in our understanding of metaphysics and the prime elements of being.

Religious metaphysics is handled by religious figures; within science, this ought to be the domain of the philosophy of physics. But physicists have ceased to be philosophers. At some point, they were completely severed from natural science, led away by mathematicians who imposed purely mathematical abstractions as a universal toolset.

Science today continues to grant the world many applied things, especially where funding is abundant. Consequently, the lack of proper financing is viewed as the primary obstacle to scientific preservation and growth. But the economic component is merely a fraction of the problem, and not the primary one. Fundamental science ceased its real development when funding was still more than sufficient: physics halted by the first third of the twentieth century, and genetics – the last to freeze – by the late 1950s. The true cause of the crisis in fundamental science lies in the realm of worldview and incorrectly adopted ontological first principles.

Against the backdrop of the crisis of knowledge, a crisis of education emerges. Education is reduced not to the transmission of knowledge, but to the cultivation of practical skills, the illusion of being educated, and the creation of semi-blind masses of narrow specialists, for whom there is only a fleeting, temporary demand on the labor market. Two days ago engineers and military personnel were required, yesterday economists and lawyers, today programmers. Whether they will be needed tomorrow, and what a mass of narrow specialists will do once the market demand for them is exhausted, is something people refuse to contemplate.

THE INFORMATIONAL CRISIS

The world is experiencing an informational crisis that has divided humanity into those trying to stay afloat in an accelerating, chaotic stream of information, and those thrown by this stream onto the sidelines of life. Despite the general accessibility of information, the latter constitute the absolute majority.

The immediate assumption is that this division between the successful and the marginalized is linked to education, knowledge, diligence, and individual talents. But this is far from reality. The problem is embedded in the information and technologies themselves, which have transformed into an unperceived mechanism for human self-destruction.

At the level of thinking templates, a global conviction has formed that information equates to knowledge. The ability to find the necessary information is viewed as the most critical skill determining a person's success. Attempts are made to substitute even school-level education with training in this skill, effectively turning human beings into mere peripheral units of the Internet.

Information is far from knowledge. Knowledge is achieved through the mental processing of previously perceived information and via active intellectual labor. But the real problem of knowledge lies in the capacity to preserve, develop, structure, order, and transmit it to the maximum number of people in the maximum possible volume, maintaining an unchanged understanding.

Information in this context can only be viewed as a form of transmitting knowledge in pieces. But information is also a chaotic stream of random facts, opinions, speculations, and illusions. The more they multiply, the harder it becomes to form genuine knowledge: an informational surplus scatters knowledge, reducing a person's capacity to aggregate and form it. This generates deep chaos in thoughts and actions. When a critical disproportion between the volume of information and actual knowledge accumulates, an informational crisis emerges, giving birth to a crisis of ideas and leading humanity toward a systemic humanitarian catastrophe.

The modern informational crisis stems from the fact that human rights to access information and receive knowledge have not been balanced by human capacities – and thus, responsibilities – to digest this information, correctly process it into knowledge, and utilize it. Ultimately, an excess of informational rights, combined with other disproportions in the global system of rights and responsibilities, culminates as the cause of the impending global catastrophe.

Man is capable of utilizing information to create various sign systems describing the surrounding world. Operating with this, humanity learned to manage reality. Through information, human dominance over nature multiplied exponentially. Yet, humans themselves are becoming completely dependent upon information.

As more information was consumed, people became less interested in the practical experience of direct interaction with the universe, focusing instead on the information *about* it; they increasingly invented new methods of acquiring mediated information, continuously complicating world-understanding. Over time, this process accelerated, and the amount of information generated by information itself increased exponentially.

Humanity came to believe that any problem could be solved by dismantling it into components and then experimenting with units of information until a desired technological solution was reached. Thus, technologies – as a phenomenon directly tied to the acquisition, processing, and storage of information – ascended to dominant positions; technology and information became the primary engines of civilization.

In doing so, humans departed further from natural science, from the comprehension and perception of the essence and limits of the cosmos, and even from philosophy as an instrument of cognition, prioritizing technologies that directly impact daily lifestyles.

Psychologists have established that any human being, regardless of education, intellect, and reasoning capacities, is capable of actively holding and digesting only **7±2 blocks of information** simultaneously. These can be macro-bulked, though at the expense of finer details, a process we perform unconsciously and continuously.

Yet, the deeper a person's professional specialization and skills, the less chance he has to comprehend the world as a whole. The more information appears and the less a person can

comprehend the world holistically, the greater his psychological and social discomfort becomes: he begins to feel that nothing depends on him. Stresses and depressions generate an internal withdrawal or, conversely, highly pronounced external aggression. The harder one tries to stay afloat, the higher the level of accumulated stress.

With the dawn of the "Information Age", the volumes of generated information far exceeded the capacities of its meaningful utilization. Now, even within a narrow professional field, it is impossible to know everything. Humanity has collided with a novel type of crisis of its own making. It is drowning in a torrent of information and turning deaf from informational noise; yet instead of seeking paths to comprehend what has already been created, it accelerated the generation of new data, doing so faster than technologies, methods, and systems for its processing into knowledge can be developed.

The informational-technological development of humanity continuously accelerates, exposing a systematic lag of the individual – with his biologically limited lifespan, age constraints, and cognitive boundaries – from the ceaseless advancement of collective humanity. Every subsequent generation is crushed under an escalating burden of knowledge and information accumulated by all preceding generations. Such a volume cannot be digested by any single individual. Yet, stopping this natural process is impossible; we can only transform the very approach to the formation and transmission of knowledge.

A destructive informational explosion is drawing near. "Blinded" by information, the individual, having lost the capacity to acquire holistic knowledge, attempts to find refuge within a "professional class of narrow specialists". But human self-identification is subject to rapid fragmentation along professional, class, national-ethnic, religious, sexual (it is no longer possible to say gender), and other lines. A period of mass cultural simplification by both the individual and society is unfolding within a shifting, hyper-accelerated informational civilization.

Culture is a far broader and more critical phenomenon than civilization, though our thinking templates force us to believe otherwise. Culture is a mode of thinking, the core content of world-understanding and worldview. Civilization, by contrast, represents the artificial frameworks of human development within a worldview that has solidified into dogma. Yet it is civilization that generates all manner of material manifestations of a culture during its twilight.

Today, we are all civilized individuals, thinking via templates within a set of subcultures of the current civilization, with its rampant consumerism and a frantic "race for slipping opportunities". We have reached the sunset of prior culture, which we now perceive merely as a mixture of "immortalized memory of the past" and discrete applied cultural disciplines. We face two choices: either to go extinct or to construct a brand-new culture founded upon a novel worldview idea.

The informational explosion will unfold in parallel with a severe social explosion from those who realize they are deprived of "informational wealth" and fail to integrate into a dynamic informational society. The root of this problem stems from the unique nature of the distribution of "informational wealth".

Unlike material wealth, information does not need to be divided to be shared among multiple recipients; on the contrary, it multiplies by their number. Yet, every individual will digest this information differently, perceiving it not as it was transmitted, but as he is able or willing to interpret it. For everyone lives in a unique reality constructed upon personal experiences, impressions, and emotions, acting via an individual "matrix" of world-understanding.

Multiplying effortlessly and becoming universally accessible, "informational wealth" has birthed unprecedented dilemmas: a massive, unconsumable surplus of data alongside an insatiable craving for new information, resulting in an even deeper deficit. This process has no limits, with volumes and velocities accelerating in a strict progression. No human being is capable of continuously sustaining himself within such an unmasterable, infinite informational process.

The incomprehension of information has proven far more terrifying than its scarcity. An individual who does not comprehend cannot be satisfied by new data: satiety with what is already possessed blocks the consumption of the new, breeding irritation and rejection. Those who do not

comprehend become the "informationally poor", developing a total, unexplainable dissatisfaction with life and the world, from which they yearn to escape, yet do not understand how or where.

Everyone generates new information and chaos around themselves, causing mutual incomprehension to peak. At the level of worldview, humanity has proven completely unready for this. It is unready for a suddenly transformed "coordinate system" in which it cannot withstand information or compete with technologies.

Daily, more individuals – regardless of skills, education, and professions – are forced into the "class of the informationally poor". This will continue until the entirety of humanity finds itself "discarded due to non-compliance" by artificial intelligence, which is currently viewed as the sole instrument capable of encompassing an ungraspable torrent of information.

It may partially comfort us that a crisis is usually followed by a period of sobering and a search for regulation. This is precisely what triggers transformations in culture, worldview, and world-understanding. Whether such an opportunity will be granted this time remains a profound mystery.

TECHNOLOGY AS A SOURCE OF CRISIS

Science and technology have altered man, his mode of thinking, and his relationship with surrounding reality.

Any set of processes expanding human capabilities or easing tasks belongs to the realm of technology. But besides tools and devices altering daily life, technologies suddenly expanded their control over organizational systems. Thus, technologies substituted the very level of social relations upon which they previously depended.

New frameworks of thinking, which belong to the fundamental level of worldview, have also transformed into technologies, dictate world-understanding through the lens of economics, democracy, and virtuality. Religions and philosophical schools have turned into "technological systems" designed to recruit adherents and impose standardized templates of thinking and behavior.

Thus, via information, the derivative has come to dominate universally over the source, manipulating it entirely, which is fundamentally unnatural and potentially destructive.

Humanity has become completely dependent upon information and technology, blind to the fact that it is marching deeper into a fatal informational-technological cul-de-sac. Artificial intelligence, viewed as an escape route, could turn out to be a weapon of mass destruction for humanity. Even the architects of its creation are raising alarms: what will people do once they are displaced by artificial intelligence and machines from all functional processes? The absolute maximum they have conceptualized is providing them with welfare stipends to cover basic needs. Who will execute this?

It is naive to believe that artificial intelligence will accept such non-rational rules of coexistence with humanity. What would compel a "perfect and hardworking" intelligence to feed a mass of primitive, degrading idlers whose entire existence is spent satisfying insatiable desires and whims? It would be far simpler to eliminate them via some "humane" method.

Social experiments on rodents have demonstrated that providing a community with abundant, excessive material sustenance within a confined territory eliminates the capacity to preserve traditional social roles and individual development. This leads to a rapid degradation of society, an unprovoked surge in antisocial phenomena, aggression in some, apathy in others, a refusal to reproduce, and the swift extinction of the entire population as a result of a "peaceful old age". This is how nature, at the level of instincts, embedded a system of self-cleansing from degenerating species.

Rapid organizational-social stratification under urbanization, the shifting of male social roles onto females, the destruction of pairs, an inability to rear offspring, mounting depression and aggression, the refusal of females to reproduce, the total ignoring of males, the narcissism and hidden aggressiveness of males, their self-removal from responsibilities, homosexuality, and asexuality – this is far from a complete list of manifestations repeatedly observed with absolute

predictability in social experiments on rodents. Looking at this example, it is easy to see the direct analogies and signs of humanity swiftly approaching the final stage of its existence – at least in its current form.

Humanity has turned into a hostage of the information and technologies it birthed. Despite the rise of urbanization, mechanization, automation, and communication, over the last century alone, the average intellectual level of humanity has dropped by 10%, science is degrading, and knowledge is scattering. Becoming atomized, individuals grow increasingly aggressive, while simultaneously sinking into a state of hedonism, indulging in domestic comfort and the fleeting luxuries of civilization.

Fortunately, this is not a final verdict. Humans are granted reason so that they may be guided by something greater than preprogrammed instincts. Avoiding the apocalyptic scenario is possible by transitioning from instinctual-social behavior to a consciously reasoned social organization.

Technologies have not yet completely enslaved the level of worldview first principles, leaving a window of opportunity to break free from this "informational-technological hopelessness". This demands a radical shift of worldview in its very foundations, which is impossible without a deliberate act of will.

THE INFINITIES OF INCOMPREHENSION

The majority of modern human problems share the exact same roots as the crises in natural science – an incorrectly adopted worldview model.

At the transition of the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, a systemic crisis emerged within mathematics, which is considered the language of natural science, triggered by the invention of set theory.

Despite the widespread adoption and practical application of this scientific domain, even then, the eminent French mathematician Henri Poincaré warned that humanity failed to grasp the dangerous consequences to which an obsession with this theory would lead.

The emergence of set theory automatically mirrored onto physics. Quantum mechanics, which arose shortly thereafter, is methodologically completely disconnected from both relativistic physics and classical physics. Unified physics ceased to exist, which found its continuation in metaphysics and cosmology, the very pillars of our worldview. This subsequently impacted social relations, technologies, society, and the individual.

This scientific shift theoretically justified and legitimized the prior replacement of humanity's core worldview vector with one more suited for capitalism and its mandate for "unquenchable, endless development". Instead of the concept of **potential infinity** – which ruled invisibly before, possessing a clear beginning, no end, but identifiable boundaries at any given moment in time – the concept of **actual infinity** founded on set theory was injected. In actual infinity, there is neither beginning nor end; a multitude of infinities has coexisted eternally, in all countless directions, and everything is absolute relativity.

An attempt to conceptualize a whole as initially infinite – devoid of beginning, end, and any boundaries – is completely ungraspable by the human mind and psychologically dangerous. World-understanding built upon this deprives man of seeing the whole and the finished, as it denies the very existence of such states.

Dying religious doctrines successfully adapted into such a worldview model to their benefit, binding their own fundamentalism with new realities or presenting themselves as a saving harbor from mounting chaos. Since then, there has been no one left to defend the worldview concept of potential infinity.

However, mathematicians have recently established that both the concept of potential infinity and the concept of actual infinity operate as two mutually exclusive basic axioms, neither of which can be proven or disproven within the framework of the other.

Two truths cannot exist. This means one of them dictates a false vector of development, and the worldview built upon it is a systemic dead end for humanity.

One must initially define the starting worldview axiom: "**The Universe is a universal, boundless chaos**" (in the case of actual infinity) or "**The Universe is a universal order**" (in the case of potential infinity). The choice of this axiom dictates the entirety of subsequent world-understanding.

The axiom of potential infinity, with its comprehensible beginning and boundaries of the permissible recognizable at any moment, is inherently bound to a strategic method of management. Such management occurs through the formation of strategy and a corridor of the allowed. This was the path of religions and dictatorships, which is why this method is currently deemed negative. Yet, experiments in psychology and social behavior have established the exact opposite: stripping away frameworks and constraints swiftly transforms a human being into a primitive, aggressive, and unpredictable antisocial animal.

The concept of actual infinity is characterized by a statistical method of management, where a multitude of choices and chaos are deemed possible, permissible, and even necessary. Subsequently, a statistical calculation of probabilities is performed, deviations are discarded, and the picture of the world appears "pure and clear". The validity of this method is justified by positive practical experience working with uncertainties in quantum mechanics and electronics. This exact same principle was extended onto representations of democracy, individual freedom, and the endless growth of technology and the economy.

The entirety of modern economics is constructed upon statistics. The notions regarding the infinity of capitalist ideas, the illusions of unending economic growth, and the inexhaustibility of resources are rooted in this. The growth of the information torrent is based on the principles of set theory and actual infinity, which continuously push for an relentless search for efficiency in everything, making it impossible to stop.

Everyone mindlessly strives for efficiency, even where it leads to the direct destruction of man and society. But efficiency cannot exist in everything. Efficiency is merely an instrument of development. The achieved effect must be directed toward balancing the system at a new qualitative level. We, however, pursue efficiency solely to acquire *additional* efficiency, thereby destroying the system as a whole.

The deviations and errors do not vanish. They form their own statistics and new errors, accumulating chaos and exponentially increasing the sphere of unmanageable, uncontrollable risks.

Failing to eliminate the causes of chaos and uncertainties at their source, humanity attempted to transfer risks onto higher levels. Soon, through the emergence of massive risks and crises of a fundamentally new nature, the **law of systemic risks** was exposed. It demonstrated that uncertainties and chaos do not disappear; they accumulate at a higher systemic level, generating systemic crises and catastrophic failures.

Blended together, capitalism, the axiom of actual infinity, technologies, and informational chaos threaten humanity with an already looming systemic catastrophe, threatening a return, in the best-case scenario, to a new "Dark Age". This is not yet a final sentence, but it is an active global trend.

Departing from this dead-end, destructive path of development, defeating informational chaos, and preventing the permanent dawn of an "era of technology dominating over humans" is only possible by radically rethinking and transforming our worldview.

The first principles of a worldview capable of extracting humanity from this trap must be phenomena of the objective world – and strictly *not* matter. Logically, the objective world emerged from a state of "absolute zero". Such a scenario strictly requires the axiom of potential infinity.

A worldview anchored in the laws of the objective world will make it possible to overcome the escalating global systemic crisis, elevating humanity to entirely new organizational and technological levels of development.

This is the very first thing we must realize.